

THE TERM AS A SIGN AND A WORD

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Abstract. *The article covers the research of the terms used both in science and professional communication. The origin of the term, its different types, the researches of various scholars have been discussed in the paper. And the categories of a scientific text have been revealed as well.*

Keywords: *term, sign, word, concept, polysemy, text, linguistics, phraseological expression, scientific prose, metaphorization, metonymization.*

ТЕРМИН КАК ЗНАК И СЛОВО

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена исследованию терминов, используемых как в науке, так и в профессиональном общении. В статье обсуждаются происхождение термина, его разновидности, исследования различных ученых. Выявлены и категории научного текста.*

Ключевые слова: *термин, знак, слово, концепт, многозначность, текст, языкознание, фразеологическое выражение, научная проза, метафоризация, метонимизация.*

INTRODUCTION

The semantic side of the term constitutes its content plan, while its expression plan is represented by a linguistic structure, the so-called “linguistic shell”, which can be considered as a form of existence of the concept. At the same time, the term can be considered a kind of sign indicating the belonging of the concept that it expresses to a particular system. It is the position that formed the basis of the semiotic approach to terminology (Theory and Practice, 1987:110).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A term is a word, not just a sign pointing to a certain element in the system.

The term, according to the definition of Fedorova I.V. is a word of a special language that serves for professional, scientific communication. It expresses a scientific concept and, in essence, must clearly define the boundary of a scientific concept in accordance with its etymology (Theory and Practice, 1987:111).

The ambiguity of the term is also manifested within the framework of one science. In terminology Ufimtseva A.A. notes that polysemy is developed in the same categories of words that have this quality as part of general literary vocabulary, “when one sign form is able to accommodate a number of contents” (Ufimtseva, 1968: 64).

The ambiguity of the term within the same science manifests itself in different ways. The development of a particular theory in any science also implies the development of appropriate terminology, which means not only the manifestation of new terms within this theory, but also the emergence of various nuances, shades of meaning in existing terms.

Polysemy reflects the natural process of development and improvement of language and thinking, since it is precisely polysemy, as A.L. Pumpyansky said. “It allows a person to use in the process of communication a limited number of linguistic means to express an unlimited number of meanings, to communicate and understand not only known, but also emerging, not yet known thoughts” (Pumpyansky, 1983:125).

The theory and practice of studying various terminological systems, as well as the experience of lexical and graphic work, indicate that the term, being a lexical unit that functions according to the laws of natural language, has polysemy.

RESULTS

In this regard, it is interesting to observe Mauer L.V. who studies the functional specificity of polysemantic terms, due to the fact that their semantic structure is formed on the basis of different types of lexis and semantic variants (Mauer L.V., 1986:24). Moreover, the lexis semantic variants of polysemantic terms as a whole function independently and carry a different load.

One of the reasons for the ambiguity of the term, according to Fedorova I.V. is so called “intercategoriality”, which consists in the fact that in the content of the concept presented in the term, signs are distinguished that are characteristic of several categories at the same time (Theory and Practice, 1987:119). This phenomenon is inherent in general scientific vocabulary.

The main reason for the emergence and replenishment of synonymic series is the polysemy of the term, namely, the ability of polysemantic terms to enter into various synonymic series.

The main source of the development of synonymy in terms are the following language processes: terminology, specialization, metaphorization and metonymization, as well as borrowing, tracing, rethinking, the use of eponyms (Theory and practice, 1987:122).

The problem of polysemy and synonymy is acutely felt when compiling reverse dictionaries, and especially when the way to define a term is not a scientific definition, but a synonymic series.

A term in the most general sense is a word in a special function. This is a word of a special language that serves for professional, scientific communication, and is associated with a concept belonging to a certain field of science or technology.

The term in the scientific text is characterized by ambiguity, in addition, in scientific prose, the phenomenon of terminological homonymy is quite common.

The analysis of units of scientific texts showed that they are based on general scientific and special terms.

The scientific text allows the use of some elements of colloquial speech as an aid. This material is selected, transformed and organized in accordance with genre features and functional tasks.

The text of linguistics is only on the way to its recognition as a branch of general linguistics. The categories of the text have not yet received sufficient clear consecration. Nevertheless, studies conducted in our country and abroad have already yielded tangible results.

According to I.R. Galperin: “A researcher of any large object, such as a text, for example, is threatened by two dangers: on the one hand, the automation of the facts of the object and, on the other hand, the globalization of the object – it is not up to the assessment of the study of individual phenomena and their essential characteristics and functions. (Galperin 1981:8). Like any new object of study, the text is understood and defined in different ways.

DISCUSSION

A text is a work of a speech – creative process that has completeness. The text as a fact of a speech act is systemic. The text is a kind of complete message that has its own content.

The content of the text as a complete whole is its information. The sentence is not a unit of text. The unit of the text is a larger unity that combines a number of sentences – this is an over-phrasal unity. Over phrasal unity in some cases, it coincides with a paragraph, in other cases, one paragraph easily breaks up into several over phrasal units.

The object of study of this article is a scientific text. Among the categories of text, we distinguish forms of dependence in the relative dependence of segments of the text in relation to the content of the entire text or part of it. Recall that as terms convenient for this work, we use the term (meaning) only for morphemes of words and phrases “meaning”, content – for the entire text or its more or less complete part. At the same time, it must be borne in mind that both meaning and meaning are subject to some kind of semantic fluctuations when they are considered as part of larger segments.

The term “meaning” is used, as I.R. Galperin, and in relation to the sentence, but only in relation to the formally structural side of this unit (Galperin: 1981:98).

The analysis of the vocabulary of a modern scientific text consists of the following categories of lexical units:

1. The word of the general literary language is, first of all, service words: prepositions and, on, from, with, with, etc.: conjunctions: which, that, therefore, or etc.: pronoun this, that etc.

2. Words of the general literary language, which are used in a scientific text, as a rule, in a narrow, special meaning. These are words such as: to be, to have, to be able, case, part, condition, etc.

3. Words characteristic of scientific texts and only occasionally used in scientific texts as borrowing, for example: analyze, classify, fix, system, function, equation, temperature, method.

4. Phraseological expression: to satisfy a need, a complex of something, causing something, equivalent to something, interaction of components, etc.

5. Special terminology of this part of the field of science, for example: structures, operation, resource, gondola cars, luggage, transportation, cargo, etc.

6. Words of the general literary language, usually not found in scientific texts, but the content of which may be the subject of scientific consideration, for example: points, transportation, safety, progress.

7. Symbols, schemes, mathematical expressions and other types of non-verbal scientific semiotics.

The dictionary of scientific works is divided into only two categories: terminology and general literary vocabulary, but at present there are three layers in it: commonly used, general scientific and terminological.

CONCLUSIONS

It is known that the main informative unit of the language of a scientific text is a term. After analyzing the technical terms, or as they are commonly called “specific” terms, we can say with confidence that they have a meaning characteristic of any one branch of knowledge, and are characterized by a simple semantic structure, the absence of commonly used meanings and synonyms, and the specialization of word-formation models for words certain semantics, there are also borrowed and international terms. When selecting the vocabulary of scientific technical literature, there should be unambiguity and accuracy, which means the absence of ambiguity and synonymy in their meanings.

Most of the scientific terms are international, because has analogues in other European languages, and in particular in Russian: base, rail, control, heavy, long.

“Technical terms” are characterized by the absence of internationalisms; they have completely passed into other languages of the world, i.e., became international: operation, refrigerated, bulk, metal.

The term is always the result of professional thinking. Therefore, specialists, representatives of the same profession, are always interested in the fact that the meaning of the term is clear and unique in its word or phrase. This improves understanding among professionals and reduces loss in perception and assimilation of information. Their meaning is mobile, the semantic boundaries of terms are changeable, accuracy and unambiguity are temporary and fragile.

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